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Case Blog

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Two violations followed by homicide

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Abstract

It's about the murder of a 13-year-old girl. His 17-year-old cousin was imputed. After the studies, it turned out that the young man according to the DSM V was structuring a histrionic and narcissistic personality.

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Development of the case

The event that took place was the discovery of a semi-naked girl in the bed of a river, dead and with signs of probable sexual abuse." "After a day of making inquiries by the police personnel, an uncle and a cousin of the girl were arrested, leaving only the young man in charge of the Juvenile Criminal Court.

After the legal procedures, the young person is referred to the offices of the expert body (psychologist and psychiatrist) of the Minority and Family Courts. The 17-year-old was the 13-year-old girl's first cousin and the case was titled "Creminis Causa homicide in real contest with aggravated sexual abuse with repeated carnal access". The adolescent was referred by the Court in order to carry out the psychological and psychiatric examinations in order to determine if it was included in the provisions of Article 34, paragraph 1 of the CP (Article 73 of the CPP) of the Argentine Republic [1], the profile of his personality.

Prior to performing the skill, the young man was asked if he agreed to participate in a clinical research project, where his personal data would be protected in its entirety. The young man gave his consent, signed the informed consent and his mother signed it. The techniques used were: three psychiatric interviews, open and semi-directed modality; Sociological evaluation and observation. Application of the Barratt Impulsivity Scale [2]; -Application of the Violence Risk Scale of Plutchik, [3] Barcelona, Madrid, Buenos Aires, Ed. Medical Ars, 2005-2006; Application of the Sensations Search Scale. Zuckerman, S. B. G [4]. Eysenck H.J and the application of the Multi-phasic Personality Inventory of Minnesota (MMPI [5] II). It arises from his life history and from the collateral interview made to the mother, that in the family dynamics in order to the parental functions, it is her parent who supervises the upbringing of the children [1]. A maternal-filial relationship of characteristics of marked affective attachment is observed. In relation to the evolutionary development of the same, medical

complications of clinical importance are not detected, that is to say, the functions of locule, ambulation and sphincter control were normal. Regarding his childhood, it was detected that he was a child with traits of shyness and introversion and repetitions of two grades, in the primary school course. Regarding the higher psychic functions, no alterations were observed in consciousness, orientation, attention and concentration, sensoperception, adopting a calm and collaborative attitude with the proposed tasks, with a language, according to the cultural level of belonging (rural environment), comprising and responds appropriately the slogans, with a structured and respondent story. Regarding his thinking, he presents a normal course, without affecting fluency and cohesion. The content of thought has a functioning of a specific type without the presence of delusional or delirious ideas. The memory does not detect quantitative or qualitative alterations at the current time. Regarding the function will and psychomotricity do not present quantitative alterations. At a qualitative level, low tolerance to frustration is detected, which can present failures in the control of impulsivity and in the management of hostility.

Critical judgment is preserved

From the evaluation of the personality [6,7] we can observe a global functioning characterized by immaturity and psycho-affective dependence, with passive-dependent characteristics in their relationships and need for affection. Self-centered characteristics are detected, with proclivity to establish superficial interpersonal relationships with acquisitive purposes. He has difficulty in the open expression of his emotions and orientation to the search for novelty. It can present feelings of covert hostility and over-controlled behaviors. It is detected that the young person oscillates between the self-control / hostility variables; detecting proclivity (in front of certain stressors) to be able to incur impulsive behaviors, self-centeredness, interpersonal distancing, tendency to transgress social norms, with little empathy, and low creative

productivity. At a cognitive level, one detects thought with concrete characteristics, with a low reflective capacity, and difficulties in the ability to self-criticize, which allow him to properly assess his participation in conflicts. In the face of the evaluation, an attitude of insight and resistance overlapping it is detected. No organicity indicators are detected from the techniques administered. The young by age and according to the rules of the DSM V [8] (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual) structuring a personality disorder of histrionic and narcissistic characteristics. At the time of the examination it was not included in the defenses of art. 34 subsection 1 of the Criminal Code of the Argentine Nation. In order to expand, it appears that the young man in question, after he was granted a return to his home, at two years committed the same offense when he was of age and under 12 years of age. For this fact is housed in a prison in the province.

Conclusions

The present case shows a reality that sadly happens in the whole world. It has not yet been possible to arrive at the reason, of these behaviors. Undoubtedly in the personality in formation, the family nucleus of origin, the meetings with peers, the lack of values and norms influence the development of the personality and to warn at an early age element that help to conform a personality adapted to the norms of each country and family, would help prevent the occurrence of these unfortunate events. Emphasis on the family, its resources, schooling and prompt consultation with specialists would prevent them.

The cousin accused of both violations followed by homicide is in the Mendoza Provincial Penitentiary with a penalty of 30 years.

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